

SYSTEMATIC REVIEW

Comparison of external, internal flat-to-flat, and conical implant abutment connections for implant-supported prostheses: A systematic review and network meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials

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ABSTRACT

Statement of problem. The implant abutment connection interface has been considered one of the major factors affecting the outcome of implant therapy. However, drawbacks of traditional meta-analyses are the inability to compare more than 2 treatments at a time, which complicates the decision-making process for dental clinicians, and the lack of a network meta-analysis.

Purpose. The purpose of this network meta-analysis was to assess whether the implant-abutment connection influences the outcome of implant-supported prostheses.

Material and methods. An electronic search was undertaken to identify all randomized clinical trials comparing the effect of at least 2 different implant abutment connection designs published from 2009 up to May 2020. Outcome variables were implant survival rate, peri-implant marginal bone loss, and biologic and prosthetic complication rates at 12 months after prosthetic loading. Relevant information was extracted, and quality and risk of bias assessed. Pairwise meta-analyses and network meta-analyses based on a multivariate random effects meta-regression were performed to assess the comparisons ($\alpha=.05$ for all analyses).

Results. For peri-implant marginal bone loss and prosthetic complications, conical interfaces were determined to be the most effective, with significant differences when compared with external hexagonal connections ($P=.011$ and $P=.038$, respectively). No significant differences were found among the implant abutment connections in terms of survival and biologic complications ($P>.05$ in all direct, indirect, and mixed comparisons).

Conclusions. After 1 year of loading, conical connections showed lower marginal bone loss and fewer prosthetic complications when compared with external hexagonal connections. However,

the implant-abutment connection design had no influence on the implant survival and biologic complication rates.

CLINICAL IMPLICATIONS

Based on this systematic review and network meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials, dental clinicians are advised to use implant systems with a conical implant abutment connection in patients with risk factors for marginal bone loss and/or prosthetic complications.

Over recent decades, the use of dental implants for oral rehabilitation has shown good long-term results in a wide variety of situations.^{1,2} Maintaining peri-implant bone tissue is essential for the long-term success of dental implants.³ Traditionally, peri-implant marginal bone loss (MBL) of less than 1.5 mm during the first year after functional loading and less than 0.2 mm annually thereafter have been assumed to be normal.^{4,5} However, the criteria for defining success in implant dentistry are controversial.⁶⁻⁸

A wide variety of dental implant designs, materials, and surface technologies, as well as surgical and prosthetic protocols, have been proposed to improve the stability of the peri-implant tissues.⁹⁻¹⁴ The implant abutment connection interface has been considered one of the major factors modulating peri-implant bone level changes.^{15,16}

Dental implant connections can be classified into external and internal, with internal connections being further divided into passive joint or flat-to-flat systems (such as triangles, hexagons, octagons) and conical or Morse taper interfaces. External connections are characterized by having the interface above the platform of the implant.¹⁷ These have been extensively used since the development of the first osseointegrated implant, the Brånemark

implant system.¹⁸ Although still widely used today, external connections have disadvantages, including micromovement at the implant abutment level, which has been proposed as a potential risk factor for biologic and mechanical complications.^{19,20} Internal connections were introduced to overcome such drawbacks. These have reduced screw loosening and screw fracture, and enhanced dissipation of loading forces along the implant walls.^{17,21,22} Moreover, in vitro studies have reported that internal connections, particularly conical ones, reduce the implant abutment gap and subsequent bacterial penetration.^{23,24} Additionally, the use of prosthetic abutments with a smaller diameter than that of the implant platform -a concept known as platform-switching- may limit vertical MBL.²⁵⁻²⁷

Since many clinical trials have compared identical or different dental implants with different connections, several meta-analyses have been published on this topic.^{17,19,28-31} However, a potential drawback of traditional meta-analyses is the inability to compare more than 2 treatments at a time, which complicates the clinician's decision-making process. Moreover, the absence of direct comparisons among more than 2 interventions means that traditional meta-analysis cannot estimate the resulting comparative benefits and drawbacks.³² Network meta-analysis (NMA), also known as multiple treatment meta-analysis or mixed treatment meta-analysis, overcomes this limitation.³³

Therefore, the aim of the present study was to analyze the relevant data from randomized clinical trials (RCTs) and assess which implant abutment connection design (external, internal flat-to-flat, or conical) is the most effective for restoring missing teeth with dental implants. Two null hypotheses were formulated: that the implant survival rate and complications (mechanical or biologic) would be similar for all the different prosthetic interface connections and that no

differences in terms of peri-implant MBL would be identified among the implant abutment connections.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This study adhered to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses for Network Meta-Analyses (PRISMA-NMA) statement³⁴ (Supplementary Table 1, available online) and was registered in the international database of prospectively registered systematic reviews in health and social care (PROSPERO) under number CRD42018099154.

The patients, intervention, comparison, outcomes, and time (PICOT) question to be addressed was: In people with missing teeth replaced by dental implants in completely or partially edentulous mandibular or maxillary alveolar arches (P), what is the effect of external, internal flat-to-flat or conical implant abutment connection design (I) on implant survival rate, peri-implant MBL, biologic complication rate, and prosthetic complication rate (O) when compared with a positive control implant abutment connection design (C) within the first 12 months of functional loading (T)?

The inclusion criteria were RCTs, including split mouth and/or multi-arm designs comparing 2 or 3 different implant abutment connection designs with a minimum follow-up of 12 months after prosthetic loading. The review excluded trials published before 2009 and/or with fewer than 10 participants/implants in the control and/or intervention group.

The primary outcome was implant survival. The secondary outcome measurements were radiographic peri-implant MBL -from prosthesis delivery to 12 months after functional loading- and biologic and prosthetic complications. Peri-implant MBL was expressed in millimeters,

whereas implant survival and biologic and prosthetic complications were expressed in absolute values and percentages.

An electronic search of the MEDLINE (OVID), the Cochrane Library (Wiley), Scopus (Elsevier), and the Web of Science (Thomson Reuters) databases up to May 1, 2020 was conducted to identify all relevant human studies published as of 2009, without language restrictions (Supplementary Table 2, available online). Additionally, nonpeer-reviewed literature was searched (OpenGrey, 2011), as well as the US National Institutes of Health (National Institutes of Health, 2000) to identify additional potential candidates to be included. The research was completed by checking the reference lists of the selected articles and reviews.

Two reviewers (O.C.-F., L.R.-P.) independently selected the studies in accordance with the inclusion criteria. A third reviewer (R.F.) resolved any disagreements. The Cohen kappa coefficient (κ) was calculated to measure the level of agreement of the reviewers. The authors were contacted when necessary for clarification of missing information. When multiple reports from the same study were identified, the first publication addressing the outcomes of interest 12 month after the prosthetic loading was included. The data were extracted independently by 2 reviewers (O.C.-F., L.R.-P.) under the supervision of a third reviewer (R.F.). Tables were created to summarize the following data (if available): author(s), year of publication, country of origin, study design and details related to participants, intervention(s), and outcomes.

As suggested in the Cochrane Handbook for Systematic Reviews of Interventions (version 5.1.0), 2 reviewers (O.C.-F., L.R.-P.) independently evaluated the risk of bias and methodological quality of each RCT by using the Cochrane Collaboration Risk of Bias Tool.³⁵ Except for the blinding domain, which was assessed separately for clinical and radiological outcomes, the others were judged at the study level.

Pairwise meta-analyses (PMA) using a random effects model were performed for the studies that directly compared different implant abutment connection designs. For dichotomous outcomes, odds ratios (ORs) with 95% confidence intervals (CIs) were used to estimate the effect of an intervention. For continuous outcomes, mean differences (MDs) and standard deviations were used to summarize the data for each group. A χ^2 P value $<.10$ and an I^2 value greater than 50% were interpreted as indicating significant heterogeneity.³⁶ Consequently, subgroups of different characteristics based on variations in the experimental treatment protocol (such as RCT design, risk-of-bias quality, insertion timing, load timing, platform-switching, and implant design) were isolated and subjected to linear meta-regression to identify them as possible sources of covariance. Had any cluster contained ≥ 10 meta-analyzed trials, publication bias analysis would have been performed.³⁵

Subsequently, an NMA was conducted to compare the implant abutment connections for each outcome variable simultaneously. To review the network geometry, a network graph was generated and analyzed: each implant abutment connection cluster was drawn as a node, and direct comparisons between them were represented by links between the nodes. The NMA was based on a multivariate random effects metaregression.³⁷ Inconsistency was assessed substantively by comparing the results obtained through PMA and NMA and statistically by fitting both consistency and inconsistency through design-by-treatment interaction models.³⁷ Outcome variables were ranked by using the surface under the cumulative ranking (SUCRA) curve.³⁸ SUCRA is a numeric presentation of the overall ranking and presents a single number associated with each treatment, with values ranging from 0% to 100%.³⁸ A high SUCRA value (close to 100) indicates that a particular implant-abutment connection is very likely to be the

best, or one of the best. Conversely, SUCRA values close to 0 suggest that the interface is probably the worst.

The statistical analysis was carried out with software programs (Stata14; StataCorp, Review Manager 5.3; The Cochrane Collaboration) ($\alpha=.05$ for all analyses).

RESULTS

The initial electronic database search returned 1363 references. Nine articles were excluded after full-text evaluation.^{16,39-46} Altogether, 18 RCTs fulfilled the eligibility criteria and were selected for qualitative and quantitative synthesis (Table 1).⁴⁷⁻⁶⁴ The reviewer agreement rate was 95.2%, with a κ coefficient of 0.88 (almost perfect agreement). A flowchart of the screening process is shown in Figure 1.

Fourteen of the 18 RCTs included were considered to have a high risk of bias.^{47,49-52,54-58,61-64} Most of the studies showed a high or unclear risk for the blinding of clinical and/or radiological outcomes. Figure 2 and Supplementary Table 3 (available online) summarize the quality of the RCTs included.

Fifty-two of the 1042 participants in the 18 studies included could not be analyzed because of dropouts within the follow-up period (weighted mean dropout rate: 2.91%). Seven of the trials meta-analyzed had a split-mouth design.^{48,51,53,55,61-63} By implant abutment connection type, 344 participants (586 implants) were treated with external interfaces, 393 (526 implants) with internal flat-to-flat designs, and 517 participants (791 implants) with an internal conical connection. The results for each individual RCT included are reported in Table 2.

The survival and biologic analyses included 18 (1903 implants in 1042 participants)⁴⁷⁻⁶⁴ and 14 RCTs (1492 implants in 820 participants),^{47-56,59-61,64} respectively (Table 2 and Fig. 3A,

B). No statistically significant differences among any of the implant abutment connections assessed were found in either the PMAs of direct comparisons or the NMA model ($P > .05$ in all direct, indirect, and mixed comparisons) (Table 3 and Supplementary Figs. 1, 2, available online).

The peri-implant MBL analysis included 18 studies involving 1585 implants in 1042 participants (Table 2 and Fig. 3C).⁴⁷⁻⁶⁴ Meta-analysis of the direct comparisons showed significantly less peri-implant MBL in conical connections when compared with external (MD: -0.25 mm; 95% CI: -0.43 to -0.05; $P = .01$; I^2 : 81%) and internal flat-to-flat (MD: -0.27 mm; 95% CI: -0.53 to -0.02; $P = .04$; I^2 : 95%) interfaces. No statistically significant differences were found between internal flat-to-flat and external designs (MD: -0.33 mm; 95% CI: -1.18 to 0.53; $P = .46$; I^2 : 95%) (Table 3 and Supplementary Fig. 3, available online). Heterogeneity was explained by differences in the methodological quality (conical versus external designs), prosthetic loading approach (internal flat-to-flat versus external), and insertion timing of the studies (conical versus internal flat-to-flat). The results were homogeneous and consistent with the overall analysis when only studies with low risk of bias, postextractive implant placement, and immediate prosthetic loading were selected (Supplementary Fig. 4, available online). The NMA model revealed statistically significant differences for the comparison between conical and external implant abutment interfaces (MD: -0.35 mm; 95% CI: -0.62 to -0.08; $P = .011$) (Table 3).

Ten of the RCTs included evaluated the prosthetic complications rate in 834 participants (1246 implants) (Table 2 and Fig. 3D).^{47,49-51,54,56,58-61} Statistically significant differences were found between conical and external implant abutment-connections in the PMAs of direct comparisons (OR: 0.36; 95% CI 0.14 to 0.92; $P = .03$; I^2 : 21%) (Table 3 and Supplementary Fig. 5, available online) and in the NMA model (OR: 0.35; 95% CI 0.13 to 0.95; $P = .038$) (Table 3).

Regarding treatment ranking, conical implant-abutment designs provided the best results for implant survival (82.9%), peri-implant MBL (96.3%), and prosthetic complications (93.9%) (Fig. 4).

For all the outcomes measured (implant survival, peri-implant MBL, and prosthetic and biologic complication rates), no significant inconsistency was identified within the evidence networks as a whole ($P > .05$) (Supplementary Table 4, available online). In addition, the direct estimate of the summary effect did not differ from the indirect estimate in most comparisons.

DISCUSSION

The NMA tested whether the implant-abutment connection had an influence on the outcome of an implant-prosthetic rehabilitation. The results indicated that conical connection groups were associated with significantly less peri-implant MBL and fewer prosthetic complications than external interfaces, without compromising implant survival; thus, the first null hypothesis was partially confirmed and the second rejected.

Nevertheless, the results of this NMA should be treated with caution because of uncontrolled factors that may also have had a direct impact on the outcomes assessed. Uncontrolled factors included implant-related (diameter, length, macroscopic design, surface treatment, and cervical roughness of the implant),^{10,25,26} surgery-related (including clinical situation, flap design, surgical trauma, insertion depth in relation to the alveolar crest, and reestablishment of biologic width),¹³ prosthesis-related (design, materials and configuration, occlusal forces, micromovements of the abutment, and loading protocol),¹¹ and patient-related (smoking habit, systemic disease, oral microbiology, individual bone pattern, and peri-implant mucosal tissue thickness).^{12,14} Only 8 of the 18 selected studies^{47,48,50,51,53,54,56,62} assessed the

impact of the implant abutment connection design when using implants with identical macro- and microdesigns. Such factors could have affected the reliability and quality of the results, thus compromising the transitivity assumption.³³ Consequently, subanalyses were used to assess the impact of the interface in association with some of these confounders.

Bias was another challenge in the review, as nearly three-quarters of the trials presented a potential risk of bias (Fig. 2). In addition, because few of the papers that were reviewed compared the same interventions, publication bias was not assessed.³⁵ In addition, internal validity might be compromised, since most of the RCTs were conducted in multiple private practices,^{47,48,60,61} and in 12 studies implant placements were performed by several surgeons and/or prosthodontists, leading to a potential operator-dependent bias.^{47-52,55-58,60,61} Finally, a priori sample size calculation was only determined in 6 of the studies,^{49,53,55,56,58,63} leading to a potentially high type-2 error (failure to reject a false null hypothesis) in the remaining trials.

Previous studies have reported that internal interfaces, particularly conical ones, are more favorable than external connections,^{21-23,27,28} possibly explaining the results observed in the present meta-analysis, which were consistent with those reported in a recent NMA in terms of peri-implant MBL.²⁹ However, 9 of the articles included in the present review were not included in that article. In addition, 5 articles selected for that article were excluded in the present study: 4 were multiple reports on the same participants,³⁹⁻⁴² and 1 was a prospective observational study.¹⁶ Additionally, in the previous meta-analysis, a quantitative analysis was not performed on the complications (technical or biologic) or the survival rate.

Although survival of an implant is the ultimate goal, maintaining bone levels is a key criterion for implant success. While peri-implant MBL was observed in all the implant abutment connections assessed, in most of the selected studies, it lay within the success criteria range

proposed in generally accepted classifications.^{4,5} Accordingly, further long-term RCTs with larger sample sizes comparing implants with the same macro- and microtopography are needed to elucidate the results obtained. Moreover, new success criteria should be developed based on MBL rates over certain time intervals rather than on the peri-implant MBL value after a given time.⁶

As the period in function increases, so does the risk of developing a complication.³⁰ For these reasons, although a minimum of 5 years of follow-up is recommended for implant survival and success assessment,⁸ the present authors decided not to introduce time as another potential confounding variable. In fact, only 1 of the selected studies mentions a follow-up period of 5 years⁴¹; the authors reported a steady state in crestal bone levels between 1 and 5 years after loading, with a pattern similar to that of peri implant MBL between conical and external interfaces.⁴¹ Interestingly, no mechanical complications were reported in the external group, but conical connections tended to develop more peri-implant diseases, although the difference was not statistically significant.

Although the implant abutment connection could be considered a risk factor for late implant failure, it has been suggested that its impact on the risk of developing biologic and/or mechanical complications is greater.¹⁹ The present review confirms this, since no differences in terms of survival were found among the connections. However, future long-term RCTs should be conducted to confirm this absence of association.

Knowledge of the mechanical and functional limitations of implant abutment connection types is essential, since they might be directly related to the success of the procedure.³⁰ Despite the short follow-up period, conical interfaces exhibited a significantly lower risk of developing prosthetic complications in comparison with external designs. Nevertheless, several confounding

factors such as screw preload torque and abutment materials could have influenced the outcomes.^{20,31}

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the findings of this systematic review and network meta-analysis of randomized clinical trials, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Conical implant abutment designs provided the best results for implant survival, peri-implant MBL, and prosthetic complications after 1 year of loading as assessed with NMA.
2. For peri-implant MBL and prosthetic complications, conical interfaces showed significant differences when compared with external hexagonal connections.

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Acknowledgments

The authors thank Mary Georgina Hardinge for English language editing assistance.

TABLES

Table 1. Studies selected for qualitative and quantitative synthesis

Authors, year, country	Design	Surgical site	Interventions	Manufacturers
Cannata, et al, 2017 Italy ⁴⁷	Multicenter	Participants partially edentulous in maxilla or mandible, requiring 1	CC	JDIcon. J Dental Care.
	RCT (parallel)	implant-supported prosthesis; residual bone height ≥ 10 mm and thickness ≥ 5 mm measured on a CT scan	IFF	JDEvolution. J Dental Care.
Canullo, et al, 2012 Italy ⁴⁸	Multicenter	Partially edentulous participants, requiring fixed implant-supported	IFF	Amplified. P-I Brånemark.
	RCT (split-mouth)	prosthesis in posterior maxilla with 2 adjacent implants; bone thickness wide enough to insert 4-mm-diameter implants	EH	External hexagon. P-I Brånemark.
Cooper, et al, 2015 USA ⁵⁷	Multicenter	Partially edentulous participants, requiring 1 or more single	CC	OsseoSpeed. Dentsply Implants.
	RCT (parallel)	implants in anterior maxilla; bone width ≥ 5.5 mm	IFF IFF + PS	NobelSpeedy Replace. Nobel Biocare. NanoTite Certain Prevail. Biomet 3i.
Cooper, et al, 2016 USA ⁵⁸	Multicenter	Participants with partial edentulism, Kennedy Class I or II in	CC	OsseoSpeed. Dentsply Implants.
	RCT (parallel)	maxilla or mandible, requiring 2 or 3 dental implants to support individual crowns; bone thickness wide enough to insert 4.5-mm- diameter fixtures	EH	Osseotite Standard. Biomet 3i.
Crespi, et al, 2009 Italy ⁵⁹	RCT	Participants requiring extraction of 1 or 2 single rooted teeth,	CC	Ankylos Plus. Dentsply Implants.
	(parallel)	replaced by dental implants; ≥ 4 mm of bone beyond root apex and preserving 4 bony walls	EH	Seven. Sweden & Martina.
Esposito, et al, 2015 Italy ⁶⁰	Multicenter	Any patient requiring 1 implant-supported prosthesis. with any type	CC	EZ plus. MegaGen Implant.
	RCT (parallel)	of bone quality and jaw location	EH	EZ plus. MegaGen Implant.

Felice, et al, 2014 Italy ⁶¹	Multicenter	Any patient. requiring at least 2 implant-supported crowns or	CC	Way Milano. Geass. y
	RCT (split-mouth)	partial fixed prostheses supported by ≤ 3 dental implants; sufficient bone volume to insert ≥ 9 -mm-long and ≥ 3.8 -mm-diameter implants	IFF	Kentron. Geass.
Glibert, et al, 2018 Belgium ⁶²	RCT (split-mouth)	Maxillary edentulous participants; sufficient residual bone volume to insert 4 implants with 4-mm diameter and 9 to 11-mm length	CC EH	Deep Conical Cylindrical. Southern Implants. External Hex. Southern Implants.
	RCT (split-mouth)	Participants partially edentulous in axilla or mandible with ≥ 2 teeth absent; sufficient residual bone volume to place ≥ 8 -mm-long and ≥ 3.5 -mm-diameter implants	CC IFF	Nobel Active. Nobel Biocare. Nobel Replace Tapered Groovy. Nobel Biocare. d
Hsu, et al, 2016 USA ⁶⁴	RCT (parallel)	Participants with single-tooth gap in esthetic zone; sufficient bone volume for single implant as measured on CT scan	CC IFF	SuperLine. Dentium. Zimmer Tapered Screw-Vent. Zimmer Dental.
	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 Germany ⁴⁹	Multicenter	Participants missing ≥ 1 teeth in maxilla or mandible; sufficient	CC
RCT (parallel)		residual bone volume to place ≥ 10 -mm-long and ≥ 3.5 -mm-diameter implants	IFF EH	NobelReplace Tapered Groovy. Nobel Biocare. NobelActive. Nobel Biocare.
Kim, et al, 2019 South Korea ⁵⁰	RCT (parallel)	Participants who need to restore single mandibular second molar; residual bone height ≥ 9 mm and thickness ≥ 9 mm measured on CT scan	CC EH	Luna. Shinhung. Sola. Shinhung.
	Menini, et al, 2019 Italy ⁵¹	Multicenter	Participants with unfavorable prognoses for maxillary or	IFF
RCT (split-mouth)		mandibular dentition demanding immediate fixed-implant prosthesis	EH	Syra. Sweden & Martina.

Peñarrocha-Diago, et al, 2013 Spain ⁵²	RCT (parallel)	Maxillary or mandibular edentulous participants; sufficient residual	CC	InHex. Mozo-Grau.
		bone volume to insert 2 to 8 implants; residual bone height ≥ 6 mm and thickness ≥ 7 mm measured on CT scan	EH	Osseous. Mozo-Grau.
Pessoa, et al, 2017 Brazil ⁵³	RCT (split-mouth)	Mandibular edentulous participants; sufficient residual bone	CC	Unitite. SIN.
		volume, measured on CT scan, to insert 4 implants 13-mm in length and 3.8-mm in diameter.	EH	Unitite. SIN.
Pieri, et al, 2011 Italy ⁵⁴	RCT (parallel)	Participants requiring extraction of 1 maxillary premolar, replaced	CC	Smiler. Samo Biomedica.
		by dental implant, with ≥ 4 mm of bone beyond root apex and preserving 4 bony walls	IFF	Smiler. Samo Biomedica.
Pozzi, et al, 2014 Italy ⁵⁵	RCT (split-mouth)	Participants partially edentulous in mandible, Kennedy Class I. II	CC	NobelActive. Nobel Biocare.
		or III, requiring ≥ 2 single implant-supported crowns; sufficient bone volumes to accommodate dental implants without augmentation procedure	EH	NobelSpeedy Groovy. Nobel Biocare.
Sanz-Martín, et al, 2017 Spain ⁵⁶	RCT (parallel)	Participants partially edentulous in posterior maxilla or mandible;	CC	Premium TG. Sweden & Martina.
		sufficient residual bone volume to place ≥ 7 -mm-long and ≥ 3.8 - mm-diameter implants	IFF	Premium SP. Sweden & Martina.

CC: Conical connection; EH: External hexagon; IFF: Internal flat-to-flat; RCT: Randomized controlled trial; PS: Platform switching

Table 2. Comparison of studies selected

	Study, year			
	Cannata, et al, 2017 ⁴⁷	Canullo, et al, 2012 ⁴⁸	Cooper, et al, 2015 ⁵⁷	Cooper, et al, 2016 ⁵⁸
Intervention				
CON1	CC	IFF	CC	CC
CON2	IFF	EH	IFF	EH
N° of implants (participants) [dropouts]				
CON1	45 (45) [0]	40 (40) [0]	48 (48) [0]	47 (19) [0]
CON2	45 (45) [1]	40 (40) [0]	93 (93) [4]	46 (20) [0]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	52.3 (16.8)	58.2 [NR]	43 (15)	55.2 (11.8)
CON2 (SD) [Range]	51.2 (17.3)		46 (16.4)	51.0 (11.0)
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CON2	Yes	No	Mixed	No
Insertion timing				
	Post-extractive & healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Delayed	Delayed	Immediate	Delayed
Prosthesis design				
	ISCs & FPDs	ISCs	Cemented ISCs	Cemented ISCs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	Yes	Yes	No	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.56 (0.53)	0.44 (0.25)	0.22 (0.28)	0.48 (0.55)
CON2 (SD)	0.60 (0.62)	1.47 (0.46)	1.26 (0.83)	0.68 (1.2)
MD (95%CI)	-0.04 (-0.28 to 0.20)	-1.03 (-1.19 to -0.87)	-1.04 (-1.24 to -0.84)	-0.20 (-0.59 to 0.19)
<i>P</i>	.745	<.001*	<.001*	.317
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	44 (97.78)	40 (100)	48 (100)	45 (95.74)
CON2 (%)	45 (100)	40 (100)	80 (86.02)	44 (95.65)
OR (95%CI)	0.33 (0.01 to 8.22)	NC	16.27 (0.95 to 279.83)	1.02 (0.14 to 7.58)
<i>P</i> -value	.496	NA	.055	.982
Biologic complications				
CON1 (%)	2 (4.44)	0 (0)		
CON2 (%)	1 (2.22)	0 (0)	NR	NR
OR (95%CI)	2.05 (0.18 to 23.41)	NC		
<i>P</i>	.565	NA		
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)			1 (2.13)
CON2 (%)	1 (2.22)	NR	NR	11 (23.91)
OR (95%CI)	0.33 (0.01 to 8.22)			0.07 (0.01 to 0.56)
<i>P</i>	.496			.012*

Table 2 cont. Comparison of studies selected

	Study, year			
	Crespi, et al, 2009 ⁵⁹	Esposito, et al, 2015 ⁶⁰	Felice, et al, 2014 ⁶¹	Glibert, et al, 2018 ⁶²
Intervention				
CON1	CC	CC	CC	CC
CON2	EH	EH	IFF	EH
N° of implants (participants) [dropouts]				
CON1	30 (22) [0]	154 (98) [7]	71 (64) [6]	42 (21) [1]
CON2	34 (23) [0]	173 (102) [2]	73 (64) [6]	42 (21) [1]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	48.7 [25 to 67]	52.5 (14.1)	52.0 [19 to 80]	65.0 [44 to 86]
CON2 (SD) [Range]		50.1 (14.5)		
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CON2	No	No	No	Yes
Insertion timing				
	Post-extractive	Post-extractive & healed sites	Post-extractive & healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Immediate	Immediate & delayed	Delayed	Immediate
Prosthesis design				
	ISCs & FPDs	ISCs. FPDs. FCDs & ODs	ISCs & FPDs	ODs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	No	Yes	No	Yes
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.2 (0.43)	0.94 (0.84)	0.73 (0.59)	0.25 (0.37)
CON2 (SD)	0.17 (0.39)	1 (1.03)	0.84 (0.59)	0.31 (0.41)
MD (95%CI)	0.03 (-0.17 to 0.23)	-0.06 (-0.37 to 0.25)	-0.11 (-0.30 to 0.08)	-0.06 (-0.23 to 0.11)
<i>P</i> -value	.772	.702	.268	.491
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	30 (100)	152 (98.70)	71 (100)	42 (100)
CON2 (%)	34 (100)	170 (98.27)	70 (95.89)	39 (92.86)
OR (95%CI)	NC	1.34 (0.22 to 8.13)	7.10 (0.36 to 139.95)	7.53 (0.38 to 150.46)
<i>P</i>	NA	.75	.198	.186
Biologic complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	2 (1.30)	1 (1.41)	
CON2 (%)	0 (0)	1 (0.58)	1 (1.37)	NR
OR (95%CI)	NC	2.26 (0.20 to 25.21)	1.03 (0.06 to 16.77)	
<i>P</i>	NA	.507	.984	
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	5 (3.25)	0 (0)	
CON2 (%)	3 (8.82)	10 (5.78)	0 (0)	NR
OR (95%CI)	0.15 (0.01 to 2.98)	0.55 (0.18 to 1.64)	NC	
<i>P</i>	.212	.281	NA	

Table 2 cont. Comparison of studies selected

	Study, year			
	Gultekin, et al, 2013 ⁶³	Hsu, et al, 2016 ⁶⁴	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 ⁴⁹	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 ⁴⁹
Intervention				
CON1	CC	CC	CC	CC
CON2	IFF	IFF	IFF	EH
N° of implants (participants) [dropouts]				
CON1	43 (21) [2]	13 (13) [0]	58 (32) [1]	59 (32) [1]
CON2	50 (21) [2]	13 (13) [0]	63 (30) [1]	41 (26) [4]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	41.3 [19 to 59]	58.5 (14.1)	49.5 (13.1)	49.5 (13.1)
CON2 (SD) [Range]		56.9 (10.9)	46.9 (14.6)	49.9 (13.6)
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CON2	No	No	No	No
Insertion timing				
	Healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Delayed	Delayed	Immediate	Immediate
Prosthesis design				
	NR	ISCs	ISCs, FDPs & FCDs	ISCs, FDPs & FCDs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	No	No	No	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.35 (0.13)	0.21 (0.56)	0.95 (1.37)	0.95 (1.37)
CON2 (SD)	0.83 (0.16)	0.74 (0.47)	0.63 (1.18)	0.64 (0.97)
MD (95%CI)	-0.48 (-0.54 to -0.42)	-0.53 (-0.93 to -0.13)	0.32 (-0.22 to 0.86)	0.31 (-0.21 to 0.83)
<i>P</i>	<.001*	.015*	.246	.247
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	43 (100)	13 (100)	56 (96.55)	57 (96.61)
CON2 (%)	50 (100)	13 (100)	60 (95.24)	40 (97.56)
OR (95%CI)	NC	NC	1.40 (0.23 to 8.26)	0.71 (0.06 to 8.13)
<i>P</i> -value	NA	NA	.489	.785
Biologic complications				
CON1 (%)		0 (0)	1 (1.72)	1 (1.69)
CON2 (%)	NR	0 (0)	1 (1.59)	1 (2.44)
OR (95%CI)		NC	1.09 (0.07 to 17.80)	0.69 (0.04 to 11.35)
<i>P</i>		NA	.953	.795
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)			5 (8.62)	4 (6.78)
CON2 (%)	NR	NR	4 (6.35)	3 (7.32)
OR (95%CI)			1.39 (0.35 to 5.45)	0.92 (0.19 to 4.35)
<i>P</i>			.636	.918

Table 2 cont. Comparison of studies selected

	Study, year			
	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 ⁴⁹	Kim, et al, 2019 ⁵⁰	Menini, et al, 2019 ⁵¹	Peñarrocha-Diago, et al, 2013 ⁵²
Intervention				
CON1	IFF	CC	IFF	CC
CON2	EH	EH	EH	EH
N° of implants (participants) [dropouts]				
CON1	62 (30) [1]	11 (11) [1]	40 (20) [0]	72 (7) [2]
CON2	41 (27) [4]	11 (11) [1]	43 (20) [0]	69 (8) [1]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	46.9 (14.6)	NR [20 to 66]	64.0 [47 to 79]	56.9 [44 to 77]
CON2 (SD) [Range]	49.9 (13.6)			
Platform switching				
CON1	No	Yes	No	Yes
CON2	No	No	No	No
Insertion timing				
	Healed sites	Healed sites	Post-extractive	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Immediate	Delayed	Immediate	Delayed
Prosthesis design				
	ISCs, FDPs & FCDs	ISCs	FCDs	FCDs & OD
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	No	Yes	Yes	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.63 (1.18)	0.04 (0.63)	1.64 (0.77)	0.12 (0.17)
CON2 (SD)	0.64 (0.97)	0.59 (0.95)	1.53 (0.83)	0.38 (0.51)
MD (95%CI)	-0.01 (-0.49 to 0.47)	-0.55 (-1.22 to 0.12)	0.11 (-0.23 to 0.45)	-0.26 (-0.36 to -0.16)
<i>P</i> -value	.968	.126	.533	<.001*
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	60 (96.77)	11 (100)	39 (97.50)	71 (98.61)
CON2 (%)	39 (95.12)	11 (100)	42 (97.67)	68 (98.55)
OR (95%CI)	1.54 (0.21 to 11.38)	NC	0.93 (0.06 to 15.36)	1.04 (0.06 to 17.03)
<i>P</i> -value	.673	NA	.959	.976
Biologic complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.39)
CON2 (%)	1 (2.44)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.45)
OR (95%CI)	0.22 (0.01 to 5.43)	NC	NC	0.96 (0.06 to 15.62)
<i>P</i>	.352	NA	NA	.976
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)	4 (6.45)	0 (0)	1 (2.50)	
CON2 (%)	3 (7.32)	2 (18.18)	2 (5.00)	NR
OR (95%CI)	0.87 (0.19 to 4.12)	0.17 (0.01 to 3.88)	0.53 (0.05 to 6.03)	
<i>P</i>	.864	.263	.606	

Table 2 cont. Comparison of studies selected

	Study, year			
	Pessoa, et al, 2017 ⁵³	Pieri, et al, 2011 ⁵⁴	Pozzi, et al, 2014 ⁵⁵	Sanz-Martín, et al, 2017 ⁵⁶
Intervention				
CON1	CC	CC	CC	CC
CON2	EH	IFF	EH	IFF
N° of implants (participants) [dropouts]				
CON1	12 (12) [0]	19 (19) [1]	34 (34) [0]	33 (19) [6]
CON2	12 (12) [0]	19 (19) [1]	34 (34) [0]	28 (18) [4]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	63.1 [18 to 75]	45.8 [26 to 67]	52.2 [39 to 59]	57.7 (11.9)
CON2 (SD) [Range]		46.6 [32 to 65]		59.7 (10.5)
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
CON2	No	No	No	Yes
Insertion timing				
	Healed sites	Post-extractive	Healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Immediate	Immediate	Delayed	Delayed
Prosthesis design				
	FCDs	Screwed ISCs	Cemented ISCs	ISCs & FPDs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	Yes	Yes	No	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.17 (0.54)	0.19 (0.17)	0.51 (0.34)	0.26 (0.22)
CON2 (SD)	1.17 (0.44)	0.49 (0.25)	1.1 (0.52)	0.11 (0.2)
MD (95%CI)	-1.00 (-1.39 to -0.61)	-0.30 (-0.44 to -0.16)	-0.59 (-0.84 to -0.34)	0.15 (0.01 to 0.29)
<i>P</i>	<.001*	<.001*	<.001*	.037*
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	12 (100)	18 (94.74)	34 (100)	33 (100)
CON2 (%)	12 (100)	19 (100)	34 (100)	26 (92.9)
OR (95%CI)	NC	0.32 (0.01 to 8.26)	NC	6.32 (0.29 to 137.37)
<i>P</i>	NA	.489	NA	.241
Biologic complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	1 (5.26)	0 (0)	2 (6.06)
CON2 (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (10.71)
OR (95%CI)	NC	3.16 (0.12 to 82.64)	NC	0.54 (0.08 to 3.47)
<i>P</i> -value	NA	.489	NA	.514
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)		0 (0)		0 (0)
CON2 (%)	NR	2 (10.53)	NR	4 (14.29)
OR (95%CI)		0.18 (0.01 to 4.00)		0.08 (0.00 to 1.58)
<i>P</i>		.278		.097

CC: Conical connection; CI: Confidence interval; CON1: Connection 1; CON2: Connection 2; EH: External hexagon; FCDs: Fixed complete dentures; FPDs: Fixed partial dentures; IFF: Internal flat-to-flat; ISCs: Implant-supported crown; NA: Not applicable; NC: Not calculable; NR: Not reported; ODs: Overdentures; OR: Odds Ratio; MD: Mean difference; SD: Standard deviation

* Significantly associated ($P < .05$)

Table 3. Results for comparisons of implant abutment connections

		PMA MBL (mm)				NMA MBL		
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	MD (95%CI)		<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	MD (95%CI)	
CC vs								
IFF	8	638	-0.27 (-0.53 to 0.02)		.04*	95%	-0.20 (-0.48,0.07)	.154
EH	9	710	-0.25 (-0.45 to -0.05)		.01*	81%	-0.35 (-0.62,-0.08)	.011*
IFF vs								
EH	3	237	-0.33 (-1.18 to 0.53)		.46	95%	-0.14 (-0.48,0.19)	.420
		PMA Survival				NMA Survival		
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	Survival rate [†]	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>
CC vs								
IFF	8	714	326/330 vs 363/384	2.21 (0.66 to 7.45)	.20	15%	1.86 (0.78 to 4.39)	.240
EH	9	923	454/461 vs 452/462	1.32 (0.48 to 3.66)	.59	0%	1.40 (0.64 to 3.06)	.449
IFF vs								
EH	3	266	121/124 vs 139/142	1.30 (0.25 to 6.62)	.75	0%	0.76 (0.29 to 1.99)	.695
		PMA Biologic complications				NMA Biologic complications		
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	Biologic rate [‡]	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>
CC vs								
IFF	6	480	7/239 vs 6/241	1.05 (0.26 to 4.22)	.89	0%	1.26 (0.48 to 3.35)	.654
EH	7	746	4/372 vs 3/374	1.23 (0.27 to 5.66)	.79	0%	1.00 (0.36 to 2.77)	1.00
IFF vs								
EH	3	266	0/142 vs 1/124	0.22 (0.01 to 5.73)	.35	NA	0.79 (0.22 to 2.80)	.730
		PMA Prosthetic complications				NMA Prosthetic complications		
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	Prosthetic rate [‡]	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>
CC vs								
IFF	5	454	5/226 vs 11/228	0.47 (0.11 to 1.92)	.29	26%	0.63 (0.17,2.32)	.216
EH	5	606	10/301 vs 29/305	0.36 (0.14 to 0.92)	.03*	21%	0.29 (0.08,1.11)	.038*
IFF vs								
EH	2	186	5/102 vs 5/84	0.75 (0.20 to 2.80)	.67	0%	0.46 (0.14,1.59)	.556

CC: Conical connection; CI: Confidence interval; EH: External hexagon; IFF: Internal flat-to-flat; NA: Not applicable; MD: Mean difference; NMA: Network meta-analysis; OR: Odds Ratio; PMA: Pairwise meta-analysis

* Significantly associated ($P < .05$)

† (number of surviving implants)/total randomized

‡ (number of prosthetic complications)/total randomized

FIGURES

Figure 1. Screening process flowchart.

Figure 2. Risk of bias assessment of studies included based on the Cochrane Risk of Bias tool.

Figure 3. Network meta-analysis graph (net diagram) Each node represents one implant abutment connection category (cluster). A, Implant survival. B, Biologic complications. C, Peri-implant marginal bone loss. D, Prosthetic complications. CC, conical connection; EH, external hexagonal; IFF, internal flat-to-flat.

Figure 4. Illustration of surface under cumulative ranking (SUCRA) analysis for implant survival, biologic complications, peri-implant marginal bone loss, and prosthetic complications. MBL, marginal bone loss.

SUPPLEMENTARY TABLES AND FIGURES

Supplementary Table 1. PRISMA NMA Checklist of items to include when reporting systematic reviews involving network meta-analysis

Section/Topic	Item #	Checklist Item	Reported on Page #
TITLE			
Title	1	Identify the report as a systematic review <i>incorporating a network meta-analysis (or related form of meta-analysis).</i> *	1
ABSTRACT			
Structured summary	2	Provide a structured summary including, as applicable: Background: main objectives Methods: data sources; study eligibility criteria, participants, and interventions; study appraisal; and <i>synthesis methods, such as network meta-analysis.</i> Results: number of studies and participants identified; summary estimates with corresponding confidence/credible intervals; <i>treatment rankings may also be discussed. Authors may choose to summarize pairwise comparisons against a chosen treatment included in their analyses for brevity.</i> Discussion/Conclusions: limitations; conclusions and implications of findings. Other: primary source of funding; systematic review registration number with registry name.	1-2
INTRODUCTION			
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the review in the context of what is already known, <i>including mention of why a network meta-analysis has been conducted.</i>	2-3
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of questions being addressed, with reference to participants, interventions, comparisons, outcomes, and study design (PICOS).	4
METHODS			
Protocol and registration	5	Indicate whether a review protocol exists and if and where it can be accessed (e.g., Web address); and, if available, provide registration information, including registration number.	4
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify study characteristics (e.g., PICOS, length of follow-up) and report characteristics (e.g., years considered, language, publication status) used as criteria for eligibility, giving rationale. <i>Clearly describe eligible treatments included in the treatment network, and note whether any have been clustered or merged into the same node (with justification).</i>	4-5

Information sources	7	Describe all information sources (e.g., databases with dates of coverage, contact with study authors to identify additional studies) in the search and date last searched.	5
Search	8	Present full electronic search strategy for at least one database, including any limits used, such that it could be repeated.	Suppl. Table 2
Study selection	9	State the process for selecting studies (i.e., screening, eligibility, included in systematic review, and, if applicable, included in the meta-analysis).	5-6
Data collection process	10	Describe method of data extraction from reports (e.g., piloted forms, independently, in duplicate) and any processes for obtaining and confirming data from investigators.	5-6
Data items	11	List and define all variables for which data were sought (e.g., PICOS, funding sources) and any assumptions and simplifications made.	5
Geometry of the network	S1	Describe methods used to explore the geometry of the treatment network under study and potential biases related to it. This should include how the evidence base has been graphically summarized for presentation, and what characteristics were compiled and used to describe the evidence base to readers.	6
Risk of bias within individual studies	12	Describe methods used for assessing risk of bias of individual studies (including specification of whether this was done at the study or outcome level), and how this information is to be used in any data synthesis.	6
Summary measures	13	State the principal summary measures (e.g., risk ratio, difference in means). <i>Also describe the use of additional summary measures assessed, such as treatment rankings and surface under the cumulative ranking curve (SUCRA) values, as well as modified approaches used to present summary findings from meta-analyses.</i>	7
Planned methods of analysis	14	Describe the methods of handling data and combining results of studies for each network meta-analysis. This should include, but not be limited to: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Handling of multi-arm trials;</i> • <i>Selection of variance structure;</i> • <i>Selection of prior distributions in Bayesian analyses; and</i> • <i>Assessment of model fit.</i> 	6
Assessment of Inconsistency	S2	Describe the statistical methods used to evaluate the agreement of direct and indirect evidence in the treatment network(s) studied. Describe efforts taken to address its presence when found.	6
Risk of bias across studies	15	Specify any assessment of risk of bias that may affect the cumulative evidence (e.g., publication bias, selective reporting within studies).	NA
Additional analyses	16	Describe methods of additional analyses if done, indicating which were pre-specified. This may include, but not be limited to, the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sensitivity or subgroup analyses; • Meta-regression analyses; • <i>Alternative formulations of the treatment network; and</i> 	6

- *Use of alternative prior distributions for Bayesian analyses (if applicable).*

RESULTS†

Study selection	17	Give numbers of studies screened, assessed for eligibility, and included in the review, with reasons for exclusions at each stage, ideally with a flow diagram.	7 Figure 1
Presentation of network structure	S3	Provide a network graph of the included studies to enable visualization of the geometry of the treatment network.	Figure 3
Summary of network geometry	S4	Provide a brief overview of characteristics of the treatment network. This may include commentary on the abundance of trials and randomized patients for the different interventions and pairwise comparisons in the network, gaps of evidence in the treatment network, and potential biases reflected by the network structure.	7-9 Figure 3
Study characteristics	18	For each study, present characteristics for which data were extracted (e.g., study size, PICOS, follow-up period) and provide the citations.	Table 1
Risk of bias within studies	19	Present data on risk of bias of each study and, if available, any outcome level assessment.	7 Figure 2
Results of individual studies	20	For all outcomes considered (benefits or harms), present, for each study: 1) simple summary data for each intervention group, and 2) effect estimates and confidence intervals. <i>Modified approaches may be needed to deal with information from larger networks.</i>	7-8 Table 2
Synthesis of results	21	Present results of each meta-analysis done, including confidence/credible intervals. <i>In larger networks, authors may focus on comparisons versus a particular comparator (e.g. placebo or standard care), with full findings presented in an appendix. League tables and forest plots may be considered to summarize pairwise comparisons.</i> If additional summary measures were explored (such as treatment rankings), these should also be presented.	8-9 Table 3 Suppl. Figure 1-3,5
Exploration for inconsistency	S5	Describe results from investigations of inconsistency. This may include such information as measures of model fit to compare consistency and inconsistency models, <i>P</i> values from statistical tests, or summary of inconsistency estimates from different parts of the treatment network.	9 Suppl. Table 4
Risk of bias across studies	22	Present results of any assessment of risk of bias across studies for the evidence base being studied.	NA
Results of additional analyses	23	Give results of additional analyses, if done (e.g., sensitivity or subgroup analyses, meta-regression analyses, <i>alternative network geometries studied, alternative choice of prior distributions for Bayesian analyses, and so forth.</i>)	8 Suppl. Figure 4
DISCUSSION			
Summary of evidence	24	Summarize the main findings, including the strength of evidence for each main outcome; consider their relevance to	9

		key groups (e.g., healthcare providers, users, and policy-makers).	
Limitations	25	Discuss limitations at study and outcome level (e.g., risk of bias), and at review level (e.g., incomplete retrieval of identified research, reporting bias). <i>Comment on the validity of the assumptions, such as transitivity and consistency. Comment on any concerns regarding network geometry (e.g., avoidance of certain comparisons).</i>	9-10
Conclusions	26	Provide a general interpretation of the results in the context of other evidence, and implications for future research.	12
FUNDING			
Funding	27	Describe sources of funding for the systematic review and other support (e.g., supply of data); role of funders for the systematic review. This should also include information regarding whether funding has been received from manufacturers of treatments in the network and/or whether some of the authors are content experts with professional conflicts of interest that could affect use of treatments in the network.	Title page

PICOS = population, intervention, comparators, outcomes, study design.

* Text in italics indicateS wording specific to reporting of network meta-analyses that has been added to guidance from the PRISMA statement.

Supplementary Table 2. PICOT database search strategy

Database	Search (May 1, 2020)
MEDLINE (OVID)	((((((((("implant abutment connection"[Title/Abstract] OR "prosthetic interface"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("external"[Title/Abstract] OR "external hexagon"[Title/Abstract])) OR "internal"[Title/Abstract] OR ("internal"[Title/Abstract] OR "internal flat-to-flat"[Title/Abstract])) OR ("internal"[Title/Abstract] OR "conical"[Title/Abstract] OR "morse-taper"[Title/Abstract])) AND (((((((("Dental Implants"[Mesh] OR "Dental Implants, Single-Tooth"[Mesh] OR "Dental Implantation, Endosseous"[Mesh] OR "Dental Implantation"[Mesh] OR "Dental Implantation, Endosseous, Endodontic"[Mesh] OR "Immediate Dental Implant Loading"[Mesh] AND ("humans"[MeSH Terms]) AND (((((((("marginal bone loss"[Title/Abstract] OR "bone loss"[Title/Abstract])) OR "survival"[Title/Abstract] OR "failure"[Title/Abstract] OR "complication"[Title/Abstract] OR "biological complication"[Title/Abstract] OR "prosthetic complication"[Title/Abstract])))))))) AND ("2009/01/01"[Date - Publication] : "2020/05/01"[Date - Publication])). For the remaining electronic databases, the key search terms used were: 'dental implants' AND ('implant abutment connection' OR 'external' OR 'internal' OR 'conical') AND ('bone loss' OR 'survival' OR 'failure' OR 'biological complication' OR 'prosthetic complication')
The Cochrane Library (Wiley)	'dental implants' AND ('implant abutment connection' OR 'external' OR 'internal' OR 'conical') AND ('bone loss' OR 'survival' OR 'failure' OR 'biological complication' OR 'prosthetic complication')
Scopus (Elsevier)	
Web of Science (Thomson Reuters)	

Supplementary Table 3. Risk of bias of studies selected

Supplementary Table 3 - Risk of bias of studies selected		
Cannata, et al, ⁴⁷		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computer generated random numbers"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"Opaque, sealed envelopes. The envelopes were opened only after the implant site was prepared"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"Outcome assessors were not blind"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"All measurements were taken by an independent, blinded assessor"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Other bias	Low risk	One of the authors serves as consultant for implant manufacturer

Canullo, et al, ⁴⁸		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Predefined randomization tables. A balanced random permuted block approach was used"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"Assignment was performed using a sealed envelope" "The surgical site was prepared [...] without previous knowledge of the type of implant to be placed"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"All measurements were made and collected by two calibrated blinded examiners"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"All measurements were made and collected by two calibrated blinded examiners"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	The study was partially funded by implant manufacturer.

		"The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest"
Cooper, et al, ⁵⁷		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Unclear risk	"Patients were randomized"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"At the moment of the implant placement, the implant type was revealed from the randomization envelope"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"An independent investigator blinded to the treatment group"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	Not specified Comment: as the implant shapes were different, the radiographic outcome assessor could not be blinded.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported

Other bias	Low risk	The study was partially funded by one of the brands assessed "The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interest"
Cooper, et al, ⁵⁸		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"A computer algorithm was used"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"Neither the participant nor the investigator was blinded in the comparison"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"Neither the participant nor the investigator was blinded in the comparison"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported

Other bias	Low risk	"The authors reported no conflicts of interest related to this study"
Crespi, et al, ⁵⁹		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that randomization was performed through a computer-generated random list
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that sealed envelopes were used to enclose the random code. However, the surgeon knew the type of implant immediately after the drilling sequence
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that the investigators who performed the clinical assessments were blinded
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"A blinded radiologist measured the changes"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	No other biases were identified

Esposito, et al, ⁶⁰		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Ten computer-generated restricted randomisation lists were created"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"The random codes were enclosed in sequentially numbered, identical, opaque, sealed envelopes. Only after the implant sites were prepared was the envelope [...] opened"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"At each centre there was a local blind outcome assessor who recorded all clinical outcome measures"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"One clinician not involved in the treatment of the patients performed all radiographic assessments without knowing group allocation"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	The trial was partially funded by the manufacturer of the implants. The manufacturer did not interfere with the

		conduct of the trial or the publication of the results
Felice, et al, ⁶¹		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Seven computer-generated restricted random lists were created"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"Random codes were enclosed in sequentially-numbered, identical, opaque, sealed envelopes. Only after the first implant site was prepared, the envelope [...] was opened"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"At each centre there was a local blind outcome assessor who recorded all clinical outcome measures"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"Measured by a single independent, experienced assessor" "The implant type [...] could be recognised on radiographs"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported

Other bias	Low risk	The trial was partially funded by the manufacturer of the implants. The manufacturer did not interfere with the conduct of the trial or the publication of the results
Glibert, et al, ⁶²		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computerized randomization scheme"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that the clinical assessors were not blinded
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that the radiological assessors were not blinded
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	One of the authors serves as a consultant for the implant manufacturer
Gultekin, et al, ⁶³		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement

Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computer pre-generated random sequence"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	Not specified Comment: as the implant shapes were different, the radiographic outcome assessor could not be blinded.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	No conflicts of interest
Hsu, et al, ⁶⁴		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that a draw of envelopes was used for randomization
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that allocation was performed according to

		identification contained in a sealed envelope before the surgical session
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that the assessors were not blinded
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that the assessors were not blinded
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	No conflicts of interest
Kielbassa, et al, ⁴⁹		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Random permuted block design with 12 assignments per block"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	High risk	"Allocated [...] by sequentially numbered, non-transparent, sealed envelopes" "The envelopes were opened as late as workable prior to surgery"

Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"All outcome measures were taken non-blinded"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"All outcome measures were taken non-blinded"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	The trial was partially funded by the manufacturer of the implants. The manufacturer did not interfere with the conduct of the trial or the publication of the results
Kim, et al, ⁵⁰		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computer pre-generated random sequence"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"The allocation was concealed by [...] an opaque envelope, and [...] opened immediately after the final drilling procedure"

Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	“This single-blind (patient-blind) [...] controlled clinical trial”
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	“This single-blind (patient-blind) [...] controlled clinical trial”
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	The trial was partially funded by the manufacturer of the implants
Menini, et al, ⁵¹		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computer pre-generated random sequence"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"Closed envelopes were prepared" "The envelopes were opened [...] after the first distal site was prepared"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified

Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"The examiners were not blinded because the different implant connections were visible on the radiograph"
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	The trial was partially funded by the manufacturer of the implants
Pessoa, et al, ⁵³		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified The authors did not reply to the question.
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified The authors did not reply to the question.
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"All examinations were performed blindly"
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	"All examinations were performed blindly"

Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	No other biases were identified
Peñarrocha, et al, ⁵²		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computer pregenerated random sequence"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that the allocation was concealed using opaque envelopes. The envelopes were opened before surgery
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that the clinical assessments were blinded and were performed by a separate investigator, independent of the surgical procedure
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that the radiological assessments were not blinded but were performed by a separate investigator, independent of the surgical procedure
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data reported and explained

Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures reported
Other bias	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that the trial was partially funded by the manufacturer of the implants. The manufacturer did not interfere with the conduct of the trial or the publication of the results
Pieri, et al, ⁵⁴		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	“A computer software program randomly assigned the participating patients”
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	“The randomized codes were enclosed in identical sequentially numbered opaque sealed envelopes” “Envelopes were opened [...] immediately before implant placement”
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Unclear risk	Not specified
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The authors kindly advised that it was impossible for the x-ray outcome assessor to be blinded as the two implant connections were clearly different

Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	The authors declared no conflicts of interest
Pozzi, et al, ⁵⁵		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Computer pregenerated random sequence"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	High risk	"Opaque envelopes were sealed according to pregenerated list"; "Immediately after flap elevation, an assistant indicated which implant had to be placed first"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Low risk	The authors kindly advised that the clinical assessors were blinded
Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	"An independent assessor made intraoral radiographs"

		Comment: as the implant shapes were different, the radiographic outcome assessor could not be blinded.
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	No missing data or excluded patients
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	No conflicts of interest
Sanz-Martín, et al, ⁵⁶		
Bias	Authors' judgement	Support for judgement
Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Low risk	"Randomization sequence using random block sizes"
Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Low risk	"Allocation concealment was kept using opaque-sealed envelopes, which were opened by 1 investigator during surgery (immediately before the implant placement)"
Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	High risk	The clinical assessors were not blinded
Blinding of radiological	High risk	The radiological assessors were not blinded

outcomes (detection bias)		
Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Low risk	All exclusions and missing data were reported and explained
Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Low risk	All outcome measures were reported
Other bias	Low risk	"The authors declare to have no conflict of interests with the materials used in the present study"

Supplementary Table 4. Inconsistency analysis through design-by-treatment interaction models

Outcome	χ^2	<i>P</i>
Implant survival	.51	.917
Biologic complications	.55	.908
Peri-implant MBL	4.63	.201
Prosthetic complications	2.47	.482

MBL: Marginal bone loss

Supplementary Figure 1. Forest plots for implant survival (odds ratio), comparing different implant abutment connections at 12 months' follow-up

Supplementary Figure 2. Forest plots for biologic complications (odds ratio), comparing different implant abutment connections at 12 months' follow-up

Supplementary Figure 3. Forest plots for peri-implant marginal bone loss (mean difference), comparing different implant abutment connections at 12 months' follow-up

Supplementary Figure 4. Subgroup analyses for peri-implant marginal bone loss (mean difference). Subsets of studies were created based on post-extractive implant placement (conical versus internal implant abutment connections), immediate prosthetic load (internal versus external implant abutment connections), and low risk of bias (conical versus external implant abutment connections)

Supplementary Figure 5. Forest plots for prosthetic complications (odds ratio), comparing different implant abutment connections at 12 months' follow-up

	Random sequence generation (selection bias)	Allocation concealment (selection bias)	Blinding of clinical outcomes (detection bias)	Blinding of radiological outcomes (detection bias)	Incomplete outcome data (attrition bias)	Selective reporting (reporting bias)	Other bias
Cannata, et al, 2017	+	+	-	+	+	+	+
Canullo, et al, 2012	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Cooper, et al, 2015	?	+	+	-	+	+	+
Cooper, et al, 2016	+	?	-	-	+	+	+
Crespi, et al, 2009	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Esposito, et al, 2015	+	+	+	+	+	+	+
Felice, et al, 2014	+	+	+	-	+	+	+
Glibert, et al, 2018	+	?	-	-	+	+	+
Gultekin, et al, 2013	+	?	?	-	+	+	+
Hsu, et al, 2016	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
Kielbassa, et al, 2009	+	-	-	-	+	+	+
Kim, et al, 2018	+	+	-	-	+	+	+
Menini, et al, 2019	+	+	?	-	+	+	+
Peñarrocha, et al, 2012	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
Pessoa, et al, 2017	?	?	+	+	+	+	+
Pieri, et al, 2011	+	+	?	-	+	+	+
Pozzi, et al, 2014	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
Sanz-Martín, et al, 2017	+	+	-	-	+	+	+

Table 1. Studies selected for qualitative and quantitative synthesis

Authors, year, country	Design	Surgical site	Interventions	Manufacturers
Cannata, et al, 2017 Italy ⁴⁷	Multicenter	Participants partially edentulous in maxilla or mandible, requiring 1 implant-supported prosthesis; residual bone height ≥ 10 mm and thickness ≥ 5 mm measured on a CT scan	CC	JDIcon. J Dental Care.
	RCT (parallel)		IFF	JDEvolution. J Dental Care.
Canullo, et al, 2012 Italy ⁴⁸	Multicenter	Partially edentulous participants, requiring fixed implant-supported prosthesis in posterior maxilla with 2 adjacent implants; bone thickness wide enough to insert 4-mm-diameter implants	IFF	Amplified. P-I Brånemark.
	RCT (split-mouth)		EH	External hexagon. P-I Brånemark.
Cooper, et al, 2015 USA ⁵⁷	Multicenter	Partially edentulous participants, requiring 1 or more single implants in anterior maxilla; bone width ≥ 5.5 mm	CC	OsseosSpeed. Dentsply Implants.
	RCT (parallel)		IFF IFF + PS	NobelSpeedy Replace. Nobel Biocare. NanoTite Certain Prevail. Biomet 3i.
Cooper, et al, 2016 USA ⁵⁸	Multicenter	Participants with partial edentulism, Kennedy Class I or II in maxilla or mandible, requiring 2 or 3 dental implants to support individual crowns; bone thickness wide enough to insert 4.5-mm-diameter fixtures	CC	OsseosSpeed. Dentsply Implants.
	RCT (parallel)		EH	Osseotite Standard. Biomet 3i.
Crespi, et al, 2009 Italy ⁵⁹	RCT	Participants requiring extraction of 1 or 2 single rooted teeth, replaced by dental implants; ≥ 4 mm of bone beyond root apex and preserving 4 bony walls	CC	Ankylos Plus. Dentsply Implants.
	(parallel)		EH	Seven. Sweden & Martina.
Esposito, et al, 2015 Italy ⁶⁰	Multicenter	Any patient requiring 1 implant-supported prosthesis. with any type of bone quality and jaw location	CC	EZ plus. MegaGen Implant.
	RCT (parallel)		EH	EZ plus. MegaGen Implant.

Felice, et al, 2014 Italy ⁶¹	Multicenter RCT (split-mouth)	Any patient. requiring at least 2 implant-supported crowns or partial fixed prostheses supported by ≤ 3 dental implants; sufficient bone volume to insert ≥ 9 -mm-long and ≥ 3.8 -mm-diameter implants	CC IFF	Way Milano. Geass. y Kentron. Geass.
Glibert, et al, 2018 Belgium ⁶²	RCT (split-mouth)	Maxillary edentulous participants; sufficient residual bone volume to insert 4 implants with 4-mm diameter and 9 to 11-mm length	CC EH	Deep Conical Cylindrical. Southern Implants. External Hex. Southern Implants.
Gultekin, et al, 2013 Turkey ⁶³	RCT (split-mouth)	Participants partially edentulous in axilla or mandible with ≥ 2 teeth absent; sufficient residual bone volume to place ≥ 8 -mm-long and ≥ 3.5 -mm-diameter implants	CC IFF	Nobel Active. Nobel Biocare. Nobel Replace Tapered Groovy. Nobel Biocare. d
Hsu, et al, 2016 USA ⁶⁴	RCT (parallel)	Participants with single-tooth gap in esthetic zone; sufficient bone volume for single implant as measured on CT scan	CC IFF	SuperLine. Dentium. Zimmer Tappered Screw-Vent. Zimmer Dental.
Kielbassa, et al, 2009 Germany ⁴⁹	Multicenter RCT (parallel)	Participants missing ≥ 1 teeth in maxilla or mandible; sufficient residual bone volume to place ≥ 10 -mm-long and ≥ 3.5 -mm-diameter implants	CC IFF EH	NobelActive. Nobel Biocare. NobelReplace Tapered Groovy. Nobel Biocare. NobelActive. Nobel Biocare.
Kim, et al, 2019 South Korea ⁵⁰	RCT (parallel)	Participants who need to restore single mandibular second molar; residual bone height ≥ 9 mm and thickness ≥ 9 mm measured on CT scan	CC EH	Luna. Shinhung. Sola. Shinhung.
Menini, et al, 2019 Italy ⁵¹	Multicenter RCT (split-mouth)	Participants with unfavorable prognoses for maxillary or mandibular dentition demanding immediate fixed-implant prosthesis	IFF EH	Shelta. Sweden & Martina. Syra. Sweden & Martina.

Peñarrocha-Diago, et al, 2013 Spain ⁵²	RCT (parallel)	Maxillary or mandibular edentulous participants; sufficient residual	CC	InHex. Mozo-Grau.
		bone volume to insert 2 to 8 implants; residual bone height ≥ 6 mm and thickness ≥ 7 mm measured on CT scan	EH	Osseous. Mozo-Grau.
Pessoa, et al, 2017 Brazil ⁵³	RCT (split-mouth)	Mandibular edentulous participants; sufficient residual bone	CC	Unitite. SIN.
		volume, measured on CT scan, to insert 4 implants 13-mm in length and 3.8-mm in diameter.	EH	Unitite. SIN.
Pieri, et al, 2011 Italy ⁵⁴	RCT (parallel)	Participants requiring extraction of 1 maxillary premolar, replaced	CC	Smiler. Samo Biomedica.
		by dental implant, with ≥ 4 mm of bone beyond root apex and preserving 4 bony walls	IFF	Smiler. Samo Biomedica.
Pozzi, et al, 2014 Italy ⁵⁵	RCT (split-mouth)	Participants partially edentulous in mandible, Kennedy Class I. II	CC	NobelActive. Nobel Biocare.
		or III, requiring ≥ 2 single implant-supported crowns; sufficient bone volumes to accommodate dental implants without augmentation procedure	EH	NobelSpeedy Groovy. Nobel Biocare.
Sanz-Martín, et al, 2017 Spain ⁵⁶	RCT (parallel)	Participants partially edentulous in posterior maxilla or mandible;	CC	Premium TG. Sweden & Martina.
		sufficient residual bone volume to place ≥ 7 -mm-long and ≥ 3.8 -mm-diameter implants	IFF	Premium SP. Sweden & Martina.

CC: Conical connection; EH: External hexagon; IFF: Internal flat-to-flat; RCT: Randomized controlled trial; PS: Platform switching

Table 2. Comparison of studies selected

	Study, year			
	Cannata, et al, 2017 ⁴⁷	Canullo, et al, 2012 ⁴⁸	Cooper, et al, 2015 ⁵⁷	Cooper, et al, 2016 ⁵⁸
Intervention				
CON1	CC	IFF	CC	CC
CON2	IFF	EH	IFF	EH
N° of implants (participants) [dropouts]				
CON1	45 (45) [0]	40 (40) [0]	48 (48) [0]	47 (19) [0]
CON2	45 (45) [1]	40 (40) [0]	93 (93) [4]	46 (20) [0]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	52.3 (16.8)	58.2 [NR]	43 (15)	55.2 (11.8)
CON2 (SD) [Range]	51.2 (17.3)		46 (16.4)	51.0 (11.0)
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CON2	Yes	No	Mixed	No
Insertion timing				
	Post-extractive & healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Delayed	Delayed	Immediate	Delayed
Prosthesis design				
	ISCs & FPDs	ISCs	Cemented ISCs	Cemented ISCs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	Yes	Yes	No	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.56 (0.53)	0.44 (0.25)	0.22 (0.28)	0.48 (0.55)
CON2 (SD)	0.60 (0.62)	1.47 (0.46)	1.26 (0.83)	0.68 (1.2)
MD (95%CI)	-0.04 (-0.28 to 0.20)	-1.03 (-1.19 to -0.87)	-1.04 (-1.24 to -0.84)	-0.20 (-0.59 to 0.19)
<i>P</i>	.745	<.001*	<.001*	.317
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	44 (97.78)	40 (100)	48 (100)	45 (95.74)
CON2 (%)	45 (100)	40 (100)	80 (86.02)	44 (95.65)
OR (95%CI)	0.33 (0.01 to 8.22)	NC	16.27 (0.95 to 279.83)	1.02 (0.14 to 7.58)
<i>P</i> -value	.496	NA	.055	.982
Biologic complications				
CON1 (%)	2 (4.44)	0 (0)		
CON2 (%)	1 (2.22)	0 (0)	NR	NR
OR (95%CI)	2.05 (0.18 to 23.41)	NC		
<i>P</i>	.565	NA		
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)			1 (2.13)
CON2 (%)	1 (2.22)	NR	NR	11 (23.91)
OR (95%CI)	0.33 (0.01 to 8.22)			0.07 (0.01 to 0.56)
<i>P</i>	.496			.012*

Table 2 cont. Comparison of the selected studies

	Study, year			
	Crespi, et al, 2009 ⁵⁹	Esposito, et al, 2015 ⁶⁰	Felice, et al, 2014 ⁶¹	Glibert, et al, 2018 ⁶²
Intervention				
CON1	CC	CC	CC	CC
CON2	EH	EH	IFF	EH
N° of implants (patients) [dropouts]				
CON1	30 (22) [0]	154 (98) [7]	71 (64) [6]	42 (21) [1]
CON2	34 (23) [0]	173 (102) [2]	73 (64) [6]	42 (21) [1]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	48.7 [25 to 67]	52.5 (14.1)	52.0 [19 to 80]	65.0 [44 to 86]
CON2 (SD) [Range]		50.1 (14.5)		
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CON2	No	No	No	Yes
Insertion timing				
	Post-extractive	Post-extractive & healed sites	Post-extractive & healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Immediate	Immediate & delayed	Delayed	Immediate
Prosthesis design				
	ISCs & FPDs	ISCs, FPDs, FCDs & ODs	ISCs & FPDs	ODs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	No	Yes	No	Yes
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.2 (0.43)	0.94 (0.84)	0.73 (0.59)	0.25 (0.37)
CON2 (SD)	0.17 (0.39)	1 (1.03)	0.84 (0.59)	0.31 (0.41)
MD (95%CI)	0.03 (-0.17 to 0.23)	-0.06 (-0.37 to 0.25)	-0.11 (-0.30 to 0.08)	-0.06 (-0.23 to 0.11)
<i>P</i> -value	.772	.702	.268	.491
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	30 (100)	152 (98.70)	71 (100)	42 (100)
CON2 (%)	34 (100)	170 (98.27)	70 (95.89)	39 (92.86)
OR (95%CI)	NC	1.34 (0.22 to 8.13)	7.10 (0.36 to 139.95)	7.53 (0.38 to 150.46)
<i>P</i> -value	NA	.75	.198	.186
Biological complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	2 (1.30)	1 (1.41)	
CON2 (%)	0 (0)	1 (0.58)	1 (1.37)	NR
OR (95%CI)	NC	2.26 (0.20 to 25.21)	1.03 (0.06 to 16.77)	
<i>P</i> -value	NA	.507	.984	
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	5 (3.25)	0 (0)	
CON2 (%)	3 (8.82)	10 (5.78)	0 (0)	NR
OR (95%CI)	0.15 (0.01 to 2.98)	0.55 (0.18 to 1.64)	NC	
<i>P</i> -value	.212	.281	NA	

Table 2 cont. Comparison of the selected studies

	Study, year			
	Gultekin, et al, 2013 ⁶³	Hsu, et al, 2016 ⁶⁴	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 ⁴⁹	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 ⁴⁹
Intervention				
CON1	CC	CC	CC	CC
CON2	IFF	IFF	IFF	EH
N° of implants (patients) [dropouts]				
CON1	43 (21) [2]	13 (13) [0]	58 (32) [1]	59 (32) [1]
CON2	50 (21) [2]	13 (13) [0]	63 (30) [1]	41 (26) [4]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	41.3 [19 to 59]	58.5 (14.1)	49.5 (13.1)	49.5 (13.1)
CON2 (SD) [Range]		56.9 (10.9)	46.9 (14.6)	49.9 (13.6)
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
CON2	No	No	No	No
Insertion timing				
	Healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Delayed	Delayed	Immediate	Immediate
Prosthesis design				
	NR	ISCs	ISCs, FDPs & FCDs	ISCs, FDPs & FCDs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	No	No	No	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.35 (0.13)	0.21 (0.56)	0.95 (1.37)	0.95 (1.37)
CON2 (SD)	0.83 (0.16)	0.74 (0.47)	0.63 (1.18)	0.64 (0.97)
MD (95%CI)	-0.48 (-0.54 to -0.42)	-0.53 (-0.93 to -0.13)	0.32 (-0.22 to 0.86)	0.31 (-0.21 to 0.83)
<i>P</i> -value	<.001*	.015*	.246	.247
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	43 (100)	13 (100)	56 (96.55)	57 (96.61)
CON2 (%)	50 (100)	13 (100)	60 (95.24)	40 (97.56)
OR (95%CI)	NC	NC	1.40 (0.23 to 8.26)	0.71 (0.06 to 8.13)
<i>P</i> -value	NA	NA	.489	.785
Biological complications				
CON1 (%)		0 (0)	1 (1.72)	1 (1.69)
CON2 (%)	NR	0 (0)	1 (1.59)	1 (2.44)
OR (95%CI)		NC	1.09 (0.07 to 17.80)	0.69 (0.04 to 11.35)
<i>P</i> -value		NA	.953	.795
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)			5 (8.62)	4 (6.78)
CON2 (%)	NR	NR	4 (6.35)	3 (7.32)
OR (95%CI)			1.39 (0.35 to 5.45)	0.92 (0.19 to 4.35)
<i>P</i> -value			.636	.918

Table 2 cont. Comparison of the selected studies

	Study, year			
	Kielbassa, et al, 2009 ⁴⁹	Kim, et al, 2019 ⁵⁰	Menini, et al, 2019 ⁵¹	Peñarrocha-Diago, et al, 2013 ⁵²
Intervention				
CON1	IFF	CC	IFF	CC
CON2	EH	EH	EH	EH
N° of implants (patients) [dropouts]				
CON1	62 (30) [1]	11 (11) [1]	40 (20) [0]	72 (7) [2]
CON2	41 (27) [4]	11 (11) [1]	43 (20) [0]	69 (8) [1]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	46.9 (14.6)	NR [20 to 66]	64.0 [47 to 79]	56.9 [44 to 77]
CON2 (SD) [Range]	49.9 (13.6)			
Platform switching				
CON1	No	Yes	No	Yes
CON2	No	No	No	No
Insertion timing				
	Healed sites	Healed sites	Post-extractive	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Immediate	Delayed	Immediate	Delayed
Prosthesis design				
	ISCs, FDPs & FCDs	ISCs	FCDs	FCDs & OD
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	No	Yes	Yes	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.63 (1.18)	0.04 (0.63)	1.64 (0.77)	0.12 (0.17)
CON2 (SD)	0.64 (0.97)	0.59 (0.95)	1.53 (0.83)	0.38 (0.51)
MD (95%CI)	-0.01 (-0.49 to 0.47)	-0.55 (-1.22 to 0.12)	0.11 (-0.23 to 0.45)	-0.26 (-0.36 to -0.16)
<i>P</i> -value	.968	.126	.533	<.001*
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	60 (96.77)	11 (100)	39 (97.50)	71 (98.61)
CON2 (%)	39 (95.12)	11 (100)	42 (97.67)	68 (98.55)
OR (95%CI)	1.54 (0.21 to 11.38)	NC	0.93 (0.06 to 15.36)	1.04 (0.06 to 17.03)
<i>P</i> -value	.673	NA	.959	.976
Biological complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.39)
CON2 (%)	1 (2.44)	0 (0)	0 (0)	1 (1.45)
OR (95%CI)	0.22 (0.01 to 5.43)	NC	NC	0.96 (0.06 to 15.62)
<i>P</i> -value	.352	NA	NA	.976
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)	4 (6.45)	0 (0)	1 (2.50)	
CON2 (%)	3 (7.32)	2 (18.18)	2 (5.00)	NR
OR (95%CI)	0.87 (0.19 to 4.12)	0.17 (0.01 to 3.88)	0.53 (0.05 to 6.03)	
<i>P</i> -value	.864	.263	.606	

Table 2 cont. Comparison of the selected studies

	Study, year			
	Pessoa, et al, 2017 ⁵³	Pieri, et al, 2011 ⁵⁴	Pozzi, et al, 2014 ⁵⁵	Sanz-Martín, et al, 2017 ⁵⁶
Intervention				
CON1	CC	CC	CC	CC
CON2	EH	IFF	EH	IFF
N° of implants (patients) [dropouts]				
CON1	12 (12) [0]	19 (19) [1]	34 (34) [0]	33 (19) [6]
CON2	12 (12) [0]	19 (19) [1]	34 (34) [0]	28 (18) [4]
Age of participants				
CON1 (SD) [Range]	63.1 [18 to 75]	45.8 [26 to 67]	52.2 [39 to 59]	57.7 (11.9)
CON2 (SD) [Range]		46.6 [32 to 65]		59.7 (10.5)
Platform switching				
CON1	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
CON2	No	No	No	Yes
Insertion timing				
	Healed sites	Post-extractive	Healed sites	Healed sites
Load timing				
	Immediate	Immediate	Delayed	Delayed
Prosthesis design				
	FCDs	Screwed ISCs	Cemented ISCs	ISCs & FPDs
Identical macro- and microtopography				
	Yes	Yes	No	No
Mean MBL				
CON1 (SD)	0.17 (0.54)	0.19 (0.17)	0.51 (0.34)	0.26 (0.22)
CON2 (SD)	1.17 (0.44)	0.49 (0.25)	1.1 (0.52)	0.11 (0.2)
MD (95%CI)	-1.00 (-1.39 to -0.61)	-0.30 (-0.44 to -0.16)	-0.59 (-0.84 to -0.34)	0.15 (0.01 to 0.29)
<i>P</i> -value	<.001*	<.001*	<.001*	.037*
Implant survival				
CON1 (%)	12 (100)	18 (94.74)	34 (100)	33 (100)
CON2 (%)	12 (100)	19 (100)	34 (100)	26 (92.9)
OR (95%CI)	NC	0.32 (0.01 to 8.26)	NC	6.32 (0.29 to 137.37)
<i>P</i> -value	NA	.489	NA	.241
Biological complications				
CON1 (%)	0 (0)	1 (5.26)	0 (0)	2 (6.06)
CON2 (%)	0 (0)	0 (0)	0 (0)	3 (10.71)
OR (95%CI)	NC	3.16 (0.12 to 82.64)	NC	0.54 (0.08 to 3.47)
<i>P</i> -value	NA	.489	NA	.514
Technical complications				
CON1 (%)		0 (0)		0 (0)
CON2 (%)	NR	2 (10.53)	NR	4 (14.29)
OR (95%CI)		0.18 (0.01 to 4.00)		0.08 (0.00 to 1.58)
<i>P</i> -value		.278		.097

CC: Conical connection; CI: Confidence interval; CON1: Connection 1; CON2: Connection 2; EH: External hexagon; FCDs: Fixed complete dentures; FPDs: Fixed partial dentures; IFF: Internal flat-to-flat; ISCs: Implant-supported crown; NA: Not applicable; NC: Not calculable; NR: Not reported; ODs: Overdentures; OR: Odds Ratio; MD: Mean difference; SD: Standard deviation

* Significantly associated ($P < .05$)

Table 3. Results for comparisons of implant abutment connections

		PMA MBL (mm)					NMA MBL	
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	MD (95%CI)		<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	MD (95%CI)	
CC vs								
IFF	8	638	-0.27 (-0.53 to 0.02)		.04*	95%	-0.20 (-0.48.0.07)	.154
EH	9	710	-0.25 (-0.45 to -0.05)		.01*	81%	-0.35 (-0.62.-0.08)	.011*
IFF vs								
EH	3	237	-0.33 (-1.18 to 0.53)		.46	95%	-0.14 (-0.48.0.19)	.420
		PMA Survival					NMA Survival	
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	Survival rate [†]	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>
CC vs								
IFF	8	714	326/330 vs 363/384	2.21 (0.66 to 7.45)	.20	15%	1.86 (0.78 to 4.39)	.240
EH	9	923	454/461 vs 452/462	1.32 (0.48 to 3.66)	.59	0%	1.40 (0.64 to 3.06)	.449
IFF vs								
EH	3	266	121/124 vs 139/142	1.30 (0.25 to 6.62)	.75	0%	0.76 (0.29 to 1.99)	.695
		PMA Biologic complications					NMA Biologic complications	
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	Biologic rate [‡]	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>
CC vs								
IFF	6	480	7/239 vs 6/241	1.05 (0.26 to 4.22)	.89	0%	1.26 (0.48 to 3.35)	.654
EH	7	746	4/372 vs 3/374	1.23 (0.27 to 5.66)	.79	0%	1.00 (0.36 to 2.77)	1.00
IFF vs								
EH	3	266	0/142 vs 1/124	0.22 (0.01 to 5.73)	.35	NA	0.79 (0.22 to 2.80)	.730
		PMA Prosthetic complications					NMA Prosthetic complications	
	Number of studies	Number of Implants	Prosthetic rate [‡]	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>	<i>I</i> ²	OR (95%CI)	<i>P</i>
CC vs								
IFF	5	454	5/226 vs 11/228	0.47 (0.11 to 1.92)	.29	26%	0.63 (0.17.2.32)	.216
EH	5	606	10/301 vs 29/305	0.36 (0.14 to 0.92)	.03*	21%	0.29 (0.08.1.11)	.038*
IFF vs								
EH	2	186	5/102 vs 5/84	0.75 (0.20 to 2.80)	.67	0%	0.46 (0.14.1.59)	.556

CC: Conical connection; CI: Confidence interval; EH: External hexagon; IFF: Internal flat-to-flat; NA: Not applicable; MD: Mean difference; NMA: Network meta-analysis; OR: Odds Ratio; PMA: Pairwise meta-analysis

* Significantly associated ($P < 0.05$)

† (number of surviving implants)/total randomized

‡ (number of prosthetic complications)/total randomized